

FLOW FRONT AND CURE MONITORING WITH FIBRE OPTIC SENSORS FOR THICK CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

During vacuum infusion processes such as VARI and VAP curved CFRP laminates exhibit flow front deviations in thickness direction. The flow path induced by curved structures varies depending on the layer. Flow lengths through outer layers are increased, leading to a flow front distortion. This can result in porosity and even in dry spots especially in thick laminates. An integrated sensor system measuring both, flow front arrival and curing, with negligible effect on the laminate textile structure, allows to generate process understanding which is used for an optimized process design. These aspects are provided by fibre optic sensors due to their small size and fibrous structure. In this study two fibre optical sensor types are investigated to measure flow front arrival in thickness direction within a vacuum infusion process and matrix curing in neat resin experiments.

The changing pressure situation at the flow front is used to detect resin arrival with fibre Bragg grating sensors. Simultaneously a Fresnel reflectometer is applied to detect flow front arrival by means of refractive index change of the surrounding medium.

In a first set of experiments the influence of compaction and sensor position on the sensor response during flow front arrival is investigated. In a second experiment Fresnel reflectometers are exploited to measure matrix curing in isothermal neat resin experiments. This is followed by fibre optical glass transition temperature measurements and the accuracy evaluation of the obtained results. Complementary differential scanning calorimeter measurements are used as a reference for the fibre optic curing experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

The high strength-to-weight ratio of carbon reinforced plastics (CFRP) explain the growing demand of this material in weight-sensitive industries such as aerospace. Complex CFRP manufacturing processes require a high degree of process knowledge. In order to meet the high standards of the aerospace industry it is mandatory to have a high part quality. This can only be achieved if processes have well-defined process windows and the manufacturing stays within these limits. By equipping processes with sensors, measurands can be documented and process parameters can be adjusted accordingly. In current CFRP manufacturing a variety of sensors are applied to measure: pressures, temperatures, curing, etc. In most cases these sensors measure at the part surface. However, in some cases the measurands at the part surface do not reflect the condition inside the laminate, e.g. flow distribution and curing gradients in thick laminates. This can result in lower part quality or scrap. In order to gain an insight in the occurring effects inside the laminate it is necessary to embed sensor. Most conventional sensing technology cannot be embedded in CFRP laminates due to their size or incompatibility with the electrically conducting carbon fibres. Fibre optical sensors (FOS) represent a technology that is suitable for embedded measurement applications in CFRP manufacturing. FOS have the advantage to be small, EMC-safe and it is possible to interrogate several sensors on one fibre at once by multiplexing. Several researchers have investigated FOS regarding

cure monitoring [1-3] and flow front monitoring with FBG [4] and Fresnel reflectometers [5]. In this study the influence of compaction and sensor position on the responds of embedded FOS during flow front arrival is investigated. Therefore FBG and Fresnel reflectometers are embedded in different layers of a vacuum infusion layup. This sensor system is then interrogated simultaneously during the infusion. Two setups are tested: One with a preheated infusion medium and one with a heated tool. Additionally the ability of Fresnel reflectometers to measure curing is investigated and the accuracy of glass transition temperature measurements with Fresnel reflectometers is determined. Therefore three Fresnel reflectometers are submerged in a neat resin sample and cured isothermally. In a subsequent heating cycle the glass transition temperature T_g is measured with the Fresnel reflectometers. The experimental results are compared to isothermal Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measurements of the T_g .

2 METHODOLOGY

Fibre Bragg grating

The strain sensitive FBG is a local periodic perturbation of the refractive index of the optical glass fibre. Light propagating through the core of an optical glass fibre is reflected by the FBG. The spatial period between two FBG perturbations determines which wavelengths of the incident broadband light are reflected. The Bragg wavelength λ_B exhibits the strongest reflection, it is described by:

$$\lambda_B = 2 \cdot n_{eff} \cdot \Lambda \quad (1)$$

n_{eff} is the effective refractive index and Λ is the spatial grating period.

Axial loads lead to elongation of the FBG grating period resulting in a wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda_B$. By measuring $\Delta\lambda_B$ the strain shift $\Delta\varepsilon$ of the optical fibre core can be determined according to Eq. 2 given the strain and temperature sensitivities S_ε and S_T are known and the temperature is constant.

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = S_\varepsilon \Delta\varepsilon + S_T \Delta T \quad (2)$$

The big advantage of FBG strain sensors over conventional electric sensors such as strain gauges is that they are EMC-save, miniature and they can be multiplexed. That means that several FBGs can be inscribed in one fibre and interrogated with one light source. In this study we use three separate singlemode glass fibres with one FBG imprinted in each fibre. The fibres have a 125 μm diameter with a 195 μm Ormocer coating diameter. The FBGs have a length of 8 mm with zero strain wavelengths λ_0 of 1549.95 nm, 1549.87 nm and 1549.86 nm. The embedded sensor fibres are applied to measure the effect of a changing strain state at the flow front arrival [8] and the influence of compaction and sensor position on the sensor signal.

Fresnel refractometer

Similar to the FBG the Fresnel reflectometer is a fibre optical sensor. It comprises of an optical fibre which is cleaved perpendicular to the fibre axis. The perpendicular fibre end generates a boundary surface between the fibre core and any surrounding medium. It can be assumed that incident light propagating through the optical fibre arrives normal to the boundary surface. This permits to apply simplified Fresnel equations to determine the refractive index of the adjacent medium n_m , given the incident intensity I_i , the reflected intensity I_r and the refractive index of the fibre core n_f is known:

$$\frac{I_r}{I_i} = \left(\frac{n_f - n_m}{n_f + n_m} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, the Fresnel reflectometer can be exploited to measure further medium properties by relating the measured refractive index n_m to the density ρ and the molecular mass of the polymer repeat unit M by the Lorentz-Lorentz equation:

$$\frac{n_m^2 - 1}{n_m^2 + 2} = \frac{N}{3M\varepsilon} \rho \beta \quad (4)$$

N is the Avogadro constant, ϵ is the free space permittivity and β is the polarisability [6]. Literature shows that Fresnel refractometers were successfully applied to measure resin degree of cure, T_g and flow front arrival [3-6]. In this study the end of a 125 μm SMF-28 singlemode fibre with a 245 μm polyacrylate cladding is stripped and cleaved to prepare a Fresnel reflectometer. The sensor is then used as a reference for the FBGs when measuring flow front arrival. Furthermore these sensors are used in neat resin curing experiments to show the ability to measure the glass transition temperature T_g and matrix curing under isothermal conditions.

Measuring system

The measuring system in this study acquires simultaneously information from up to four fibre optic sensors and three thermocouples (Figure 1). The fibre optic sensor interrogation is realised by a four channel device from fos4X GmbH. The device guides broadband light with a centre wavelength of 1550 nm into the singlemode fibres. The reflected light of each fibre is split into two branches with a 50/50 coupler. Before both branches are guided onto photodiodes, one branch is guided over an edge filter whereas the other branch remains unfiltered. The device realises FBG interrogation by processing the intensity ratio of both photodiodes. Fresnel reflectometer measurements can be realised by exploiting light intensity data from the unfiltered branch.

In this case we interrogated two, respectively three, FBGs and one Fresnel reflectometer ($n_f=1.4681$). The sample rate of the device is set at 50 kHz and the obtained signals are averaged over 1 Hz. Temperature measurements are realised with three type K thermocouples (TC). The TCs are read out with a TC-08 device from Pico Technology Ltd. The sensor data from both devices is synchronised at a sample rate of 1 Hz with a LabVIEW interface.

Figure 1: Measuring system

Infusion experiments

The flow front experiments are conducted in a vacuum assisted infusion process on a flat glass tool. The preform has a size of 150 mm x 250 mm made up of 18 layers of a Saertex biaxial carbon fibre non crimped fabric with a $[+45^\circ|-45^\circ]_s$ layup and an areal weight of 400 g/m^2 . The infusion is performed in a horizontal direction in order to monitor the flow front through the glass tool. The preform is equipped with sensors in the 1st, the 9th and the 17th layer to cover the whole cross section as depicted in Figure 2. The fibre optic sensors are positioned centrally on each layer and are held in place with small paper stickers several centimetres away from the FBG. On the 1st layer a FBG and a Fresnel reflectometer are placed next to each other. The Fresnel reflectometer acts as a reference flow front detector. In addition two TC are placed on the 1st layer. One TC is placed at the inlet, the other in close proximity to the fibre optic sensors. The 9th and 17th layer are both equipped with one FBG and an additional TC in the 17th layer. In order to protect the fragile optical fibres the ingress is realised by blunt cannulas which are integrated in the sealing tape. The cannulas bridge any gap between sealing tape and the dedicated preform layers. The cannula entrance itself is sealed by a small amount of sealing tape. The preform is covered with peel ply, membrane, suction fleece and vacuum foil. The infiltration medium is vegetable oil ($n_m=1.473$) in place of resin since it allows to reuse the embedded fibre optic sensors while exhibiting similar viscosity during infusion.

In order to investigate the influence of different strain states that are induced on the FBGs due to different process temperatures two separate experiments are conducted. Experiment A is conducted at ambient tool temperature and with preheated oil at 100 °C. During infiltration the oil is removed from the oven and is exposed to ambient temperature. In experiment B the tool is heated up to 120 °C and the infusion is conducted with oil at ambient temperature. The measurement is started prior to evacuation in order to monitor the sensor responds during compaction. After a steady pressure of 5 mBar is reached and the sensor signals have stabilised the infusion is started. The end of the experiment is marked by the completed infusion.

Figure 2: Infusion experiment setup

Curing experiments

In the curing experiments the degree of cure of an epoxy resin is determined with fibre optic sensors. The experiments are conducted in an oven of a Mettler Toledo HS82 hot-stage system. The oven and the sensor setup is depicted in Figure 3. The hot-stage system is equipped with Peltier elements which allow fast heating ramps and steady conditions for isothermal measurements. Three Fresnel reflectometer connected to the fibre optic device are positioned on an object plate inside the heating chamber and the whole setup is preheated at 180 °C for 10 min. Subsequently the oven is opened and a sample of EPS 600 epoxy resin is placed on the Fresnel reflectometer which is then covered by a cover glass. After closing the heating chamber the data acquisition of the hot-stage system and the fibre optic device is started synchronously and the curing reaction is logged for 5400 s to obtain a high degree of cure. After that the oven temperature is lowered to 100 °C at 10 K/min. Then the sample is heated up to 250 °C at 20 K/min. The aim of this heating run with steady heating rates is to obtain a well-defined glass transition by generating stable conditions before, during and after the expected T_g .

Figure 3: Curing experiment setup

Since the glass transition temperature is an indicator for the degree of cure and since it is especially sensitive towards higher degrees of cure the fibre optical curing curve is compared to T_g results obtained in DSC measurements. The DSC experiments are performed on a Q2000 device from TA Inc. For each run approximately 10 - 15 mg of 1-component epoxy resin Bakelite EPS 600 is placed and sealed in DSC pans. Isothermal curing runs with different duration (700 s, 1500 s, 2000 s, 3000 s, 5400 s) are conducted to generate samples with different thermal history. Each sample is then cooled rapidly to -30°C and heated up subsequently to 300 °C at 10 K/min in order to determine T_{g,DSC}. Additional non-isothermal curing runs from -50 °C to 285 °C at 5 K/min are conducted to obtain the glass transition temperature of zero conversion T_{g,0} and to fully cure the samples. This is followed by two temperature cycles from 285 °C to 150 °C and back to 285 °C to obtain results for the glass transition temperature of total conversion T_{g,∞}. Two cycles are conducted to check whether the T_{g,∞} is not rising which means the sample is fully cured.

3 RESULTS

Infusion experiments

The measurement results of experiment A with preheat oil at 100 °C and ambient tool temperature are depicted in Figure 4. The graph shows the sensor signals of the three embedded FBGs and the Fresnel reflectometer over time. After the layup is finished (t= 0 s) it can be noticed that the FBGs are subject to strain since the wavelengths have shifted towards higher wavelengths. The Fresnel reflectometer signal has not changed significantly during sensor placement. In the idle state before evacuation all four sensors show relatively stable signals. As soon as vacuum is drawn (t=800 s) all four fibre optic sensors exhibit a relative change in their sensor signal. The FBGs in the 1st layer and 17th layer show oppositional behaviour, meaning the strain on sensor in the 1st layer was relieved whereas the strain on 3rd layer has increased. The FBG in the central layer exhibits a shift towards lower wavelengths meaning the strain was relieved. After a constant vacuum pressure of 5 mBar is reached all fibre optic sensors show stable signals until the oil infusion is started (t = 2000 s). As soon as oil reaches the Fresnel reflectometer a sharp signal drop can be noticed (t = 2013 s). This drop can be explained by a difference of the refractive indices of oil and air ($n_{oil} > n_{air}$) leading to a much lower reflected intensity according to Eq. 3. Soon after the start of the infusion a decline in all FBG signals is noticeable (t = 2000 s), reaching a global minimum at t = 2033 s. During this decline the exhibiting wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda$ is between 0.10 nm and 0.70 nm. After the FBG signals pass through the minimum, the signals rebound towards higher strains reaching a plateau after the preform is filled (t = 2200 s). The observed strain behaviour of embedded FBGs at the flow front is similar to the results obtained by [7]. Analysis of the temperature data (Figure 5) reveals that the FBG strain starts to decrease as soon as the oil reaches the inlet even before it actually reaches the FBG (t = 2000 s). Yenilmez [8] showed that the preform thickness drops due to the lubrication effect when the flow front passes through. Afterwards the thickness and the resin pressure increase again. This effect leads to a FBG strain relief as the flow front propagates towards the FBG, leading to a minimum when it reaches the FBG. After the flow front passes through the compaction steadies again resulting in an increased FBG strain.

Figure 4: Wavelength-Intensity-Time plot of experiment A

Figure 5: Wavelength-Temperature-Time plot of experiment A

The measurement results of experiment B with oil at ambient temperature and tool temperature at 120 °C are depicted in Figure 6. The graph shows the sensor signals of embedded FBGs in the 1st and 17th layer and a Fresnel reflectometer. The FBG in the 9th layer failed and cannot be evaluated. After the sensors are placed in the layup the heating is started at $t = 101$ s. It can be noticed that the FBGs are subject to strain since the wavelengths have shifted towards higher wavelengths. A steady strain increase can be noticed until vacuum is drawn at $t = 472$ s when all three fibre optic sensors show a change in sensor signal. Likewise in experiment A an oppositional FBG behaviour of the sensors in the 1st and 17th layer can be noticed, with a strain relief of the FBG in the 1st layer and a strain increase of the FBG in the 17th layer. The infusion is started at $t = 2826$ s after a vacuum pressure of 5 mBar and a tool temperature of 120 °C is reached. As can be seen in Figure 6 the FBG signal drops ($\Delta\lambda = 0.33 \dots 0.60$ nm) soon after the infusion is started. At $t = 2886$ s the Fresnel reflectometer shows a large intensity drop as soon as the flow front arrives at the sensor. At the same moment the FBG exhibit a strain minimum. After the flow front passes through, the FBG strain level rebounds again. These observation match with the results from experiment A. At the end of infusion the FBG in the 1st layer reaches a steady strain level whereas the FBG in the 17th layer exhibits a slight strain decline after the rebound. Analysis of the temperature data (Figure 7) reveal a steady temperature decline at

the preform top which explains the FBG strain decline due to the temperature strain dependency. At $t = 2765$ s the oven is opened shortly before infusion resulting in a temperature drop of the TC in the top layer and at the inlet. At $t = 2765$ s a steeper temperature drop to $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is noticed as soon as the cold oil reaches the TC at the inlet. The other TCs in the bottom and top layer show only slight temperature declines which indicates that the infusion medium attains ambient temperature soon after infusion. This means that temperature strains provoked by cold infusion media play a minor role for flow front monitoring with FBG sensors in typical resin infusion processes for the aerospace industry. Note: Missing data in Figure 6 is due to failed data acquisition between 1718 s and 1857 s.

Figure 6: Wavelength-Intensity-Time plot of experiment B

Figure 7: Wavelength-Temperature-Time plot of experiment B

Curing experiments

The results from the isothermal curing experiments in the hot-stage system are depicted in Figure 8. The curing reaction starts immediately after the resin sample is exposed to the oven temperature of 180 °C. All three Fresnel refractometers show an s-shaped curing curve which reach a plateau at $t = 3000$ s. At $t = 5400$ s the oven is cooled down to 100 °C with a constant cooling ramp of 10 K/min. Simultaneously the intensity increases which is attributed to a rising resin density according to Eq. 4. After reaching 100 °C the sample is heated up to 250 °C with a constant heating ramp of 20 °K/min ($t = 5900$ s). A reverse effect can be noticed with a declining intensity attributed to a change in resin density. A kink in the intensity slope can be observed at $t = 6200$ s. In Figure 9 the kink is analysed by plotting the intensity over the temperature. It can be explained by a sudden increase of the specific volume while passing through the glass transition temperature T_g [2]. Since the specific volume is the reciprocal of density we expect a kink in intensity according to Eq. 4. The optically measured $T_{g,\text{Fresnel}} = 206.4 \text{ °C} \pm 0.6 \text{ °C}$ is in the same range as the $T_{g,\text{DSC}} = 203.4 \text{ °C} \pm 0.2 \text{ °C}$ obtained by two 180 °C isothermal DSC runs. The T_g is determined at the midpoint of the extrapolated onset and end point of the glass transition temperature range.

Figure 8: Intensity-Temperature-Time plot of the curing experiment

Figure 9: Intensity-Temperature plot of the curing experiment

$T_{g,DSC}$ generated from isothermal curing runs for 700 s, 1500 s, 2000 s, 3000 s, 5400 s and total conversion are shown in Table 1 together with the normalized glass transition temperature $T_{g,norm,DSC}$ generated from the quotient of $T_{g,DSC}$ and $T_{g,\infty}$. In Figure 10 $T_{g,norm,DSC}$ values and the Fresnel reflectometer signals from the isothermal curing run are plotted over time. The intensity axis limits are adjusted to visualise the functional dependency between intensity and glass transition temperature stated in Eq. 3 and Eq. 4. During curing the $T_{g,norm,DSC}$ development follows an s-shaped trend that is proportional to the Fresnel reflectometer signal. At higher curing times the glass transition temperature reaches a plateau where the T_g increases only slowly. This is due to the limited amount of crosslinking partners of the epoxy resin at the end of the curing reaction.

Table 1: Glass transition temperatures for different curing times at 180 °C

		0 s	700 s	1500 s	2000 s	3000 s	5400 s	∞
$T_{g,DSC}$	(°C)	-5.5	14.3	92.3	150.3	194.6	203.4	213.4
$T_{g,norm,DSC}$	(-)	-0.03	0.07	0.433	0.705	0.913	0.954	1

Figure 10: Intensity-Normalised Tg (DSC)-Time plot of the curing experiment

4 CONCLUSION

The infusion experiments showed that Fresnel reflectometer sensors are very suitable for flow front measurements due to the refractive index difference between infusion medium and air / vacuum. Results showed that compaction had only minor effects on the light intensity during vacuum infusion and the intensity signal was generally stable which can be attributed to the rigid fibre ingress via the cannula. For that reason the arriving flow front was clearly detected by a sharp intensity drop.

The Fresnel reflectometer intensity drop coincided with a FBG strain relief ($\Delta\lambda = 0.1...0.7$ nm), followed by a strain rebound. It shows that the flow front can be identified by this characteristic FBG strain behaviour and that the strain relief effect starts well before the flow front actually reaches the FBG position. The results indicate that the characteristic behaviour occurs irrespective of the strain state prior to infusion, irrespective of the sensor position in the layup and irrespective of process temperatures. Therefore fibre optic Fresnel and FBG sensors are suitable for embedded flow front measurements in thick laminates.

Curing experiments with three Fresnel reflectometers demonstrated the capability of Fresnel reflectometers to monitor curing. It was shown that the reflected sensor intensity rises proportionally to the glass transition temperature obtained in DSC measurements. Further it was shown that the glass transition temperature can be measured with Fresnel reflectometers during heating ramps. Heating

cycle results from three simultaneously interrogated Fresnel reflectometers show a variation of the $T_{g,Fresnel}$ by ± 0.6 °C with a 3 °C offset from $T_{g,DSC}$ obtained in DSC measurements.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Cusano, A.; Breglio, Giovanni; Giordano, M.; Calabrò, A.; Cutolo, A.; Nicolais, L. (2000): An optoelectronic sensor for cure monitoring in thermoset-based composites. In: *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical* 84 (3), S. 270–275
- [2] Giordano, M.; Laudati, A.; Russo, M.; Nasser, J.; Persiano, G. V.; Cusano, A. (2004): Advanced cure monitoring by optoelectronic multifunction sensing system. In: *Thin Solid Films* 450 (1), S. 191–194.
- [3] Aduriz, X. A.; Lupi, C.; Boyard, N.; Bailleul, J.-L.; Leduc, D.; Sobotka, V. et al. (2007): Quantitative control of RTM6 epoxy resin polymerisation by optical index determination. In: *Composites Science and Technology* 67 (15-16), S. 3196–3201.
- [4] Balvers, J. M. (2014): In situ strain & cure monitoring in liquid composite moulding by fibre Bragg grating sensors. Dissertation. Delft University of Technology, Delft.
- [5] Antonucci, V.; Giordano, M.; Nicolais, L.; Calabrò, A.; Cusano, A.; Cutolo, A.; Insera, S. (2003): Resin flow monitoring in resin film infusion process. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on the Advanced Materials Processing Technology, 2001* 143–144 (0), S. 687–692.
- [6] Cusano, A.; Cutolo, A.; Giordano, M.; Nicolais, L., "Optoelectronic refractive index measurements: application to smart processing," *Sensors Journal, IEEE* , vol.3, no.6, pp.781,787, Dec. 2003
- [7] Gupta, Nitesh; Sundaram, Ramesh (2009): Fiber optic sensors for monitoring flow in vacuum enhanced resin infusion technology (VERITY) process. In: *Special Issue: 15th French National Conference on Composites - JNC15* 40 (8), S. 1065–1070.
- [8] Yenilmez, Bekir; Senan, Murat; Murat Sozer, E. (2009): Variation of part thickness and compaction pressure in vacuum infusion process. In: *Composites Science and Technology* 69 (11-12), S. 1710–1719.